

Implementation of Child Care Service Standards at UPT Social Services for Children and the Elderly Siborongborong North Tapanuli

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ABSTRACT

Every human being has the right to an adequate standard of living, and a child is no exception. As a concrete manifestation of the government's efforts and concern in overcoming the problem of neglect, the government established LKSA such as Pelsos Anak which is a solution for parenting services by providing a place for abandoned and underprivileged children. This study aims to determine the Implementation of Child Care Service Standards conducted by UPT Pelsos Anak dan Lansia in Siborongborong District, North Tapanuli and uses qualitative research methods with descriptive types. This research data was obtained through interviews, observation, and documentation. The results of this study concluded that the implementation of childcare services was in accordance with Permensos No. 30 of 2011 concerning National Standards for Child Care for LKSA and in the implementation of childcare service programs was in accordance with the theory of Program Implementation according to David C. Korten.

INTRODUCTION

Every human being has the right to an adequate standard of living, and a child is no exception. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child affirms that every child has the right to adequate support for their development in terms of physical, moral, mental, social and spiritual aspects. When a man is born into the world until he closes his eyes, he needs the affection and protection of people. However, not many people have and enjoy a decent life (United Nations Convention in Wulandari, 2012).

During 2013, there are indications that the Indonesian family environment still tends to be colored by a number of family problems that are not very conducive to the future of Indonesian children. Various cases involving families remain unresolved which leaves many children without equal rights. Abandoned children are an example that not all children get the love of both parents and do not get the right to learn and play. Children become abandoned due to divorce, orphans, conflicts, and natural disasters so that they do not have parental supervision which is in the sense of neglected (Indonesian Child Protection Commission in Hasanah, 2017). The family environment is the initial base of life for every human being and is the main place for children to obtain rights. The rights of children according to Joni Tanamas in the Category of Children's Rights, (2020) are the right to maintain survival, the right to developmental, the right to get protection, and the right to participate in building their future (participation).

The result of abandoned children is that children are unable to attend education that should be carried out according to the child's age. When the situation of abandonment of orphans and children from underprivileged families occurs without any countermeasures, it is feared that children will become frustrated, feel humiliated and will rebel against the situation. As compensation, they will commit actions that lead to deviant behavior that can disturb themselves, others, and society because of the lack of education they get (Bungin & Burhan in Situmorang, 2018).

As a concrete manifestation of the government's efforts and concern in overcoming this problem, the government established Child Welfare Social Institutions such as Child Social Services which are a solution for caregiving services by providing places for abandoned and underprivileged children. This program has a function as a shelter for children. Children are given food and water every day and given education fees, shelter and alternative services that can replace family functions, so that social disorders can be limited as much as possible and children will feel living in their own family environment.

One of the government institutions that provides guidance for abandoned and underprivileged children is UPT Social Services for Children and the Elderly Siborongborong. This institution is a technical implementation unit as a government role under the auspices of the North Sumatra Provincial Social Service, which specifically provides Care, Guidance and Reduction of School Dropout Rate (illiteracy) for abandoned and underprivileged children in accordance with Permensos No. 4 of 2020 concerning Basic Social Rehabilitation for Abandoned Children (Pre-Research, 2023).

IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODS

During their time as foster children at UPT Social Services for Children and the Elderly Siborongborong, children get parenting service programs in the form of boarding, guidance, coaching, health, education and socialization of the values of life in society, religious values, customs, and empowerment through skills. Children are prepared mentally and socially to be able to live in society and achieve their ideals as the future successors of the nation.

The program implementation model is the model revealed by David C. Korten (in Harirah et al, 2020). This model uses a learning process approach and is better known as the program implementation suitability model. David C. Korten states that a program will be successfully implemented if there is a conformity of the three elements of program implementation as follows:

1. Compatibility between the program and the beneficiaries, namely the compatibility between what is offered by the program and what is needed by the target group. For example, in a children's orphanage there are music club and art club service programs, but some children have other hobbies or hobbies, so this program must be tailored to the needs of foster children. For example, providing questionnaires about hobbies or hobbies and making a program that can be accepted according to the needs of the target group of children.
2. Compatibility between the program and the implementing organization, namely the compatibility between the tasks required by the program and the capabilities of the implementing organization. For example, there is a physical guidance service program for foster children but the implementing organization does not have competent human resources in their fields, so it is necessary to match the program with the implementing organization.
3. Compatibility between the user group and the implementing organization, namely the compatibility between the conditions decided by the organization to be able to obtain program outputs and what can be done by the program target group. For example, in orphanages, children who make conditions for entry into the orphanage must include a letter of application from the family so that they can be accepted at the orphanage in order to receive the output of the program carried out by the orphanage. But in the case and in fact many children who do not have families then where do they make the letter. For conditions like this, compatibility between the beneficiary group and the implementing organization is needed, such as providing opportunities for children to still be able to enter institutions that really do not have families based on the reset carried out by the implementing organization (Korten in Sinaga, 2022).

The method that researchers use in this study is descriptive research with a qualitative approach. According to Nasir (1999) in Sugiyono (2013), this method emphasizes the aspect of deepening data in order to get the quality of the results of a study and relies on descriptive descriptions of words or

sentences that are arranged systematically starting from collecting data to interpreting and reporting research results. And aims to make a description or description of the facts, properties and relationships between the phenomena investigated (Nasir in Sugiyono, 2013). This research was conducted at UPT Social Services for Children and the Elderly Siborongborong North Tapanuli located at the Children's Social Service Institution on Jalan Tugu No.61, Pasar Siborongborong Village, Siborongborong District, North Tapanuli Regency,

North Sumatra Province. Researchers conducted research at UPT Social Services for Children and Elderly Siborongborong North Tapanuli because of the author's interest in knowing how the activities and implementation of social care services for social children carried out by UPT Social Services for Children and Elderly Siborongborong North Tapanuli.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Childcare Service Standards

Based on data analysis from the results of research conducted by researchers on the Implementation of Child Care Service Standards in UPT Social Services for Children and the Elderly Siborongborong, researchers concluded that: In the implementation of UPT Child and Elderly Social Services Siborongborong children's care services have been in accordance with the standards of childcare services in social welfare institutions according to Permensos No. 30 of 2011, but there are several indicators that have not been maximally in accordance with several standards such as:

1. Parenting services in dormitories, UPT has carried out childcare in children's homes.
2. Service with the role of a substitute for parents, UPT in performing its duties UPT has been responsible for the fulfillment of children's rights.
3. Service with the dignity of children as human beings, UPT recognizes and values children as whole individuals and ensures that every child is protected from all discrimination.
4. Child protection, UPT prohibits all forms of violence in the institution including in the enforcement of discipline and also ensures that administrators and officers who work do not have a criminal record or life history of violence.
5. Child development, UPT provides opportunities for children to develop their potential and increase children's self-confidence in the institution.
6. The identity of the child, belun in accordance with the maximum where the UPT supports and legalizes every child in the dormitory to have a legal and complete identity but has not run according to maximum standards because there are still foster children who should have a Resident Identity Card (KTP) but do not have an ID card and the UPT has not directed them to make an ID card and facilitate it.
7. Child relations, that UPT supports children to participate in various activities in the orphanage and outside the orphanage, children are also given communication facilities with family, relatives and teachers with certain time limits.

8. Child participation, that UPT encourages children to express opinions and participate in discussing various important matters concerning children's interests.
9. Food and clothing, in the implementation of childcare services consume food that maintains nutritional quality and nutrition according to the needs of children their age. However, for overall clothing is not appropriate and fulfilled, for example, sportswear that will be used during physical development every Friday has not been fulfilled. But for daily clothes, school uniforms, worship clothes are sufficient.
10. Access to education and health, UPT facilitates children to attend formal education both in institutions and in schools or other organizations. For health, it is not optimally appropriate because UPT has P3K available in children's homes, but nurses do not stay in children's homes that take care of children if the child suddenly falls ill but stays in the elderly home.
11. Children's Privacy/Confidentiality, UPT has regulations to protect children's privacy and private matters for children.
12. Timing children, UPT supports children in making their time management schedules, children are given hours of rest, play and study according to the child's ability.
13. Children's activities/work in Children's Social Welfare Institutions, UPT prohibits children from being employed in the orphanage, because in general the age of children like them must focus on learning and improving their social functioning.
14. Rules, discipline, and sanctions in Panti, children together with administrators and staff formulate various rules that they consider important for life together.

B. Program implementation

The implementation of the childcare service program at UPT Social Services for Children and the Elderly Siborongborong is in accordance with the theory of Program Implementation according to David C. Korten.

1. First, the compatibility between the program and the beneficiaries, where in the implementation of childcare service standards the program provided is in accordance with the needs of children. However, there are some standard indicators that are not yet in line with the maximum. Appropriate programs or activities in childcare services include: boarding care, services with a role as a substitute for parents, Services with the Dignity of children as human beings, Child protection, Child development, , Child relations, Child participation, Food, Access to education, Privacy/Confidentiality of children, Regulation of children's timing, Children's activities/work in Children's Social Welfare Institutions, Rules, discipline, and sanctions in the Panti. The standard indicators that are not maximally appropriate are children's identity, clothing, access to health.
2. Second, the suitability of the program with the implementing organization where in the implementation of the Child Care Service

program has paid attention to the compatibility between the program and the implementing organization, namely UPT Social Services for Children and the Elderly Siborongborong, where the activities or programs implemented are in accordance with the capabilities of the implementing organization, namely from the UPT Social Services for Children and the Elderly Siborongborong. The activities of the Childcare Service program are carried out because UPT is aware and able to carry out their social responsibilities.

3. Third, the suitability of the implementing organization with the beneficiaries, which in the implementation of the Child Care Service program has paid attention to the suitability between the group of beneficiaries, namely child beneficiary citizens within the scope of the Children's Orphanage and the implementing organization, namely UPT Social Services for Children and the Elderly Siborongborong. . But not with the condition of children who are really abandoned because UPT will accept prospective children to become their foster children only if the child has the following conditions: birth certificate, certificate of disability from the local village, photocopy of family card. So that prospective foster children who can be accepted are only children who are able to complete the requirements and files. The implementation of the Child Care Services program is carried out by meeting physical needs, social, spiritual who are responsible by UPT Social Services for Children and Elderly Siborongborong and produce output, as well as children who are beneficiaries meet the requirements decided by UPT Social Services Children and Elderly Siborongborong.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on data analysis from the results of research conducted by researchers on the Implementation of Child Care Service Standards in UPT Social Services for Children and the Elderly Siborongborong, researchers concluded that: In the implementation of parenting services UPT Social Services for Children and the Elderly Siborongborong children have been in accordance with the standard of childcare services in social welfare institutions according to Permensos No. 30 of 2011, but there are some indicators that are not in accordance with the maximum in some standards.

The implementation of the childcare service program at UPT Social Services for Children and the Elderly Siborongborong is in accordance with the theory of Program Implementation according to David C. Korten. First, the compatibility between the program and the beneficiaries, where in the implementation of childcare service standards the program provided is in accordance with the needs of children.

Second, the suitability of the program with the implementing organization where in the implementation of the Child Care Service program has paid attention to the compatibility between the program and the implementing organization, namely UPT Social Services for Children and the Elderly Siborongborong. Third, the suitability of the implementing organization

with which beneficiaries in the implementation of the Service program Child Care has paid attention to the compatibility between the beneficiary group, namely child beneficiary citizens within the scope of the Children's Orphanage and the implementing organization, namely UPT Social Services for Children and the Elderly of Siborongborong.

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